

MANUFACTURING OF NEW COPPER/VAPOUR GROWN CARBON NANOFIBRES (VGCFs) COMPOSITES FOR HEAT MANAGEMENT OF POWER ELECTRONICS

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SUMMARY: Carbon nanofibers possess outstanding thermophysical properties. Thus they are considered as an optimal reinforcement or filler of MMCs for the future high power electronics, in which higher temperatures are achieved so better thermal management are required. Their tailored coefficient of thermal expansion, low density and high thermal conductivity make this kind of metal matrix nanocomposite an ideal heat sink material for high power and high frequency electronic devices. The present work gives an overview of a manufacturing approach for Cu/VGCFs composites and a preliminary physical and microstructural characterisation. Two main manufacturing routes have been assessed: the first one is based on the deposition of copper onto the surface of nanofibres by an electroless chemical deposition process; the second one is based on the dispersion and mixing of VGCFs with copper nanopowders (50 nm) as matrix. Both routes are followed by a final consolidation step, performed by hot-pressing under high vacuum. Preliminary characterisation shows encouraging results for the use of this material in high power electronics.

KEYWORDS: copper matrix composites, vapour-grown carbon nanofibers, thermal management, power electronics, microstructure, scanning electron microscopy, thermal conductivity, coefficient of thermal expansion.

INTRODUCTION

Devices for high power electronic applications increase cyclically their inner temperature as a consequence of their own operation. Traditionally, the way to dissipate heat from electronic devices (chips, boards, etc...) is carried out by passive strategies, which mean by the use of high thermal conductivity metals, such as copper or silver, as heat sinks. Nevertheless, large mismatches in coefficient of thermal expansion in between the heat sink (17 and 19 ppm/°C for Cu and Ag respectively) and the electronic substrate leads to thermo-mechanical fatigue in the junction, thus finally leading to premature failure of devices. In conclusion, CTE and thermal conductivity of heat sinks have to be engineered for every specific application; otherwise lifetime of electronic devices can be limited dramatically. In order to find a solution to this problem, during the past decades [1] several advanced materials have been developed that combine low CTE and high thermal conductivity, from alloys like CuW, CuMo... , that possess medium thermal conductivity and tailored CTE; or alloys like Invar®, Kovar®... with although possesses good tailored CTE, have high densities and very limited thermal conductivities. In the last years some fibre reinforced MMCs have been also developed,

allowing CTE reduction at considerably high thermal conductivity. In this group there are numerous studies of MMCs with micrometric carbon fibres [2,3,4] in which the CTE mismatch with electronic substrates is notably improved while the thermal conductivity can achieve values of around 400W/mK in the best case of copper reinforced with long carbon fibres in the longitudinal direction. This is because conductivity of conventional reinforcement is frequently lower than those of metals, except for some highly graphitic carbon fibres or diamond particles, but at an extremely high cost.

Carbon nanofibers, also known as “Vapour grown carbon nanofibres – VGCFs” are one of the most promising materials as filler of metals for thermal management of high power electronics, being their thermal conductivity as high as 2000 W/mK [5] and their CTE slightly negative along the fibre length. Next table 1 gives an overview of thermal properties of a variety of advanced metal and metal matrix composites for electronic packaging applications. Values reported in this table for VGCFs, CNTs and composites based on them are obtained from theoretical calculations.

Matrix		Reinforcement Type	Vol %	Density g/cm ³	CTE 10 ⁻⁶ /K	Thermal conductivity W/mK
METALS						
W/Cu	75/25		0	15.7	8.5	236
Mo/Cu	75/25		0	9.8	9.0	180
Al/Si	50/50		0	2.5	11.0	140
W/Ni/Cu	95/3.5/1.5		0	18.0	4.5	173
Cu/Invar/Cu			0	8.3	6.5	138(XY); 40(Z)
Cu/Mo/Cu			0	9.8	6.0	210(XY); 170(Z)
COMPOSITES						
C fibre		-	0	1.8	L=4-5, T=-1	100-500
Carbon Nanotubes (SWCNTs)		-	0	2	-1.0	6600
Vapour Grown C Fibres		-	0	1.8-2	-1.0	1950
Carbon		VGCF	70	1.8-2		910
Carbon		VGCF	39	1.8-2		736
Epoxy		C fibre	60	1.85	-1.1	310 (XY)
Epoxy		VGCF	73	1.87		661
SiC		VGCF	20	2.9		310
Copper		Diamond	50	5.35	5.5	420
Copper		C fibre	28	7.2	6.5	290 (XY)
Copper		CNTs	50	5.45	-	1024
Copper		VGCF	50	5.45	5.5	840
Copper		C particles	40	5.9	9-10	150-300
Copper		C particles	50	5.9	8-9	150-300
Copper		C particles	60	7-8	7-8	150-300
Beryllium		BeO	-	-	6.1	320
Aluminium		C fibre long	75	2.02	6.5	290 (XY)
Aluminium		VGCF	37	2.44	5	642
Aluminium		C fibre short	40	2.40	4.0	230
Aluminium		B fibre	20	2.6	12.7	180
Aluminium		SiCp	60	2.9	9-10	180
Aluminium		Graphite p.	50-70	2.2-2.0	6.5-9.5	190-270

Table 1: Summary of physical properties of the most promising MMCs for electronic applications.

However, although CNTs shows considerably higher conductivity (higher than 6000W/mK is reported), VGCFs provide much better availability and performance-cost ratio for industrial production of electronic packaging components. Due to their tailorable CTE, low density and high thermal conductivity, VGCFs reinforced MMCs constitute an ideal material for heat sinks in high power and high frequency electronic devices working at much higher temperatures, such as those based on new GaAs and GaN semiconductors.

Several attempts have been carried out during the last years to use VGCFs as a reinforcement in polymers for several purposes [6,7,8]. Nevertheless, few studies have been successfully carried out using VGCFs (few micrometers in diameter after graphitization) as reinforcement in a metallic matrix [5,9]. Many problems not yet fully overcome, such as dispersion of nanofibres, blending nanofibres and metallic powders, absence of wettability between carbon and copper, compaction, sintering, etc., make the production of this material a really challenging task but, at the same time, a really interesting development with huge potential use in industrial components.

PROCESSING ROUTES

One of the main drawbacks in VGCFs handling and mixing with a matrix is dispersion. By its nature, with high aspect ratio (L/d) and Van der Waals attracting forces, VGCFs tend to keep entangled in big clusters difficult to disperse in any media. However, some other difficulties, such as absence of wettability between carbon and most of molten metals, absence of reactivity with some matrices (such as the case of copper), or density mismatches with most of metallic matrices, makes it very difficult to apply production routes of metal matrix composites in liquid state (stir-casting, rheocasting or liquid infiltration of porous performs) [10, 18]. Therefore, the most interesting manufacturing routes are those based on powder metallurgy and its many variants, in which the matrix is handled in powder state and composites are consolidated in solid state. However, dispersion of nanoreinforcements inside the matrix, and more in particular VGCFs, is a problem that has to be addressed and solved before arriving to encouraging results, that means the lowest porosity values in the composites consolidated.

It is important to underline that the present investigation is focused towards the manufacturing optimisation of Cu/VGCFs for electronic packaging applications, so a reasonable target for volume fraction of reinforcement inside copper will be always over 20%vol. in order to minimise CTE on composite samples and match it with electronic substrates as much as possible. Most of the work carried out in the present investigation is based on the use of VGCFs supplied by APSCI (Pyrograf Products, 60-150 nm in diameter and 30-100 μm in length) and conventional copper powder.

First steps of the present investigation were focused towards the application of conventional powder metallurgy procedures. In these experiments VGCFs were blended with micrometric copper powder (Ecka granules, mean size 45 μm) in “Turbula Mixer”, aided with and without the use of small Zirconia balls (2mm in diameter). This results in an inhomogeneous mixture, poor disentanglement and to excessive damage of the nanofibers as well. Figure 1 shows SEM images of typical clusters and broken fibres after the first mixing step.

Preliminary dispersion test were also carried-out by VGCFs predispersion in N-Methyl Pirrolidone (NMP) and then subsequently mixed with copper powders. These results were very similar to the previous ones, having also in mind that VGCFs and Cu powders are quite different in size, being this mismatch several orders of magnitude higher than diameter of nanofibres.

Figure 2 shows the results obtained after consolidation of blends of copper and VGCFs obtained by the above mentioned method. It clearly shows the presence of VGCFs clusters that were not infiltrated by copper, thus leading to composites with very poor characteristics. These clusters were observed by AFM techniques, confirming the absence of copper matrix inside.

Fig. 1: SEM images of Cu/VGCFs blends after mixing in turbula mixer: (a) big cluster of nanofibers, (b) fibre damaged onto a copper particle.

Fig. 2: SEM images taken from Cu/VGCFs composites after consolidation: (a) 3%vol. of VGCFs, (b) 30%vol. of VGCFs.

In order to improve these poor preliminary results, other manufacturing techniques were assessed. In particular, as the reactivity between filler and matrix does not exist during the consolidation process, this can lead to materials with inappropriate interface. Thus, it is necessary to address those manufacturing techniques that improve this aspect, which means those processes that promote a good contact between matrix and reinforcement. In this way VGCFs were coated by copper by the so-called electroless plating technique [11], which is also reported for coating nanometric reinforcements [12, 13, 14]. There are some other techniques for coating nanofibers; nevertheless this was selected due to its simplicity and because it does not need expensive facilities. This technique is based on a chemical reaction leading to the deposition of metallic elements on top of the substrate. Prior to the coating process it is necessary to catalyse the surface of VGCFs. Thus, the fibre is immersed in two catalysing baths composed by hydrochloric acid and Tin (sensitizing bath), followed by a bath containing hydrochloric acid and Palladium (activation bath). After catalysing, nanofibers are soaked into the coating solution, in which the red-ox reaction is carried-out. This results in a metallic copper deposition onto the surface of nanofibers. By this route several samples were performed. Processing conditions are described in Table 2. The whole catalysing process was aided by the application of ultrasounds into the baths, so the coating was done under turbulent flow by mechanical stirring up to 2000 R.P.M.. VGCFs were rinsed and filtered at the end of each step and finally dried under vacuum at 100 °C. As Arai and Endo suggested [15], polyacrylic acid (PAA) surfactant increases VGCFs dispersion in the co-deposition with

copper by electrodeposition. In this way this agent, PAA (Aldrich), was added to the plating bath in 140 $\mu\text{m}/\text{l}$ concentration.

Step	Composition	Concentration	Time
Sensitization	HCl	40 ml/l	30 Min
	SnCl ₂	10 g/l	
Activation	HCl	0,5 ml/l	30 Min
	PdCl ₂	0,25 g/l	
Plating	CuSO ₄	10 g/l	Up to end of reaction
	NaK(COO) ₂ (CHOH) ₂ 4H ₂ O	50 g/l	
	NaOH	10 g/l	
	HCHO	15 ml/l	

Table 2: Catalysing and Plating baths characteristics

The cover thickness and therefore the vol. % of the copper matrix in the final composite were controlled by means of VGCFs concentration into the plating bath. Finally, copper coated VGCFs are consolidated into dense samples by hot pressing. Thus, composite powders were inserted in a high strength graphite die (25 mm inner diameter) and hot-pressed under high vacuum at 25 MPa and 1000 °C for 2 hours.

In order to enable a better mixing process between VGCFs and the matrix, another interesting manufacturing route was carried-out by the use of copper nanopowders as matrix (Argonide, 50nm). Due to their pyrophoric nature, Cu nanopowders must be handled under controlled atmosphere or into organic solvents. VGCFs were predispersed into NMP by ultrasounds stirring at 60°C for six hours, in a concentration of 0,16 g/l. Copper nanopowders were added to this solution and mixing was performed by combination between mechanical stirring and filtration. In this way nanoparticles are trapped between the gaps formed by nanofibers tangles. Nevertheless, most part of the nanopowders forms little clusters, so the mixture was ultrasonicated in ethanol for 40 min. Samples were rinsed with distilled water and dried in vacuum. Consolidation was completed with the same conditions as for the previous processing route.

RESULTS

VGCFs and pure copper have a density of 2 g/cm³ and 8,93 g/cm³ respectively. In this way deviation from theoretical density was calculated. This value shows the porosity percent in the consolidated composite samples. Table 3 shows densities and porosity values obtained for each different vol. % of reinforcement and processing routes.

Route	Vol. % of reinforcement	Density (g/cm ³)	Porosity %
Electroless	20	7,21	3,96
Electroless	40	5,54	7,12
Copper nano	20	7,15	4,82
Copper nano	40	5,41	11,60

Table 3: Characteristics of consolidated samples

The porosity degree is increased proportionally to vol. % of reinforcement, since the higher content of nanofibre the more entanglement is attained, and thus the quantity of gaps to fill by copper is higher. It is clear that the consolidation of copper coated VGCFs leads to more

dense composites, this can be attributed to a better distribution of copper around the VGCFs prior to consolidation..

Fig.3 illustrates the microstructure of the samples before sintering. These SEM images have been obtained in secondary electron imaging (SEI) mode. Fig. 3(a) shows that nanofibres are homogeneously and continuously coated along the whole fibre surface. Small areas of irregular copper coating are also observed, suggesting dendritic copper growth normal to the fibre. At the same time, fig. 3(b) shows homogeneous distribution between VGCFs and copper nanoparticles, still forming some of them small clusters, however their size is smaller than the fibre diameter.

Fig. 3: SEM images of samples before hot-pressing: (a) coated nanofibers (20 vol. %), (b) nanopowder mixture (40 vol. %).

Figure 4 shows SEM images of the samples after hot-pressing. Samples were polished and then etched with FeCl_3 acid solution for 7 seconds. Sections showed are those normal to the pressing direction. Figure 4(a) illustrates a sample with 20 vol. % by electroless plating. Figure 4(b) shows 20 vol. % composite processed by nanopowders mixture.

Fig. 4: SEM images of the samples before hot-pressing: (a) coated nanofibers (20 vol. %), (b) nanopowder mixture (20 vol. %).

In figure 4(a) can be observed that coated VGCFs are homogeneously dispersed within the composite, and suitable consolidation is achieved. However there are still tiny pores, which volume is very small in sum. This is in accordance with porosity values of table 3. Fig. 4(b) shows very different microstructure. The distribution of fibers is not so homogeneous, being some of the uncoated fibres in close contact along its surface. It can also be seen small copper grains in between the fibres. The microstructure of these grains has been exposed after

etching, revealing grain growth from 50 nm before consolidation up to few micrometers after consolidation. This could be caused by excessive atomic diffusion due to the high consolidation temperature (near 1000°C), or by partially reaching melting temperature of copper during consolidation, since nanoparticles possess lower melting temperature [16, 17]. However this has to be confirmed. It can also be observed 2D orientation of the fibres, normal to the press direction. This configuration is usually known as random planar [2], and is connected with pressing, that force nanofibers to turn during consolidation. Both processing routes cause VGCFs shortening, caused either in ultrasonication step or during consolidation. The same results were obtained in 40 vol. % of reinforcement samples.

Fig. 5: (a) AFM image of 20 vol. % coated fibres after consolidation (b) EDS analysis of the same sample.

Fig. 5(a) shows AFM (atomic force microscopy) image of the fig. 4(a) sample, before etching. It can be seen that coated fibres form a kind of fibres network, that leads to the same conclusions as explained above. An EDS (energy dispersive scanning) spectrum in fig. 5(a) revealed that few oxides are formed at the end of the processing route and there is no contamination during manufacturing. These oxides are both CuO and Cu₂O as XDR in fig. 6 reveals.

Fig. 6: XRD of coated VGCFs after hot-pressing

CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

Two processing routes for VGCFs reinforced copper matrix composites have been studied and assessed: through coating by electroless plating and by wet mixing with copper nanopowders. Consolidation step is the same for both routes, and it is performed by high vacuum hot pressing. The first route, by electroless plating, leads to composite materials with lower remaining porosity at higher vol % of reinforcement. Microstructures are very different for both routes. The VGFCs coating process leads to composites with better homogeneity and improved consolidation level. VGCFs are shortened during the manufacturing process, while they show a random planar configuration. This will result in anisotropic properties of the final nanocomposite. Minimum oxide amount is formed at the end of the process, which will be beneficial for the final thermophysical properties (CTE and thermal conductivity). Microstructure observed and physical properties measured suggest that the manufacturing processes here addressed are both suitable for the production of copper matrix composites reinforced by VGCFs and other type of nanoreinforcements (CNTs, nanoparticles, etc...) although a further reduction of remaining porosity and oxide formation would lead to better thermophysical properties. Further work will also address some other critical characteristics of composites, such as interface modification by coating and/or functionalisation of fibres without degrading their physical properties in order to promote a better coupling of matrix and reinforcement, thus leading to improved physical and mechanical characteristics. Nowadays an extensive thermophysical characterisation is being carried out on samples manufactured for the development of electronic packaging for high power of wide band-gap semiconductors (GaN).

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